
EVALUATING LECTURERS' TEACHING COMPETENCIES FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN EBONYI STATE TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

Dr. Chinedu Ifeanyi Obiora

Department of Educational Foundations, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The persistent high rate of graduate unemployment in Nigeria has negatively impacted national economic growth, with about 80% of university graduates struggling to secure employment annually. Between 2006 and 2017, the unemployment rate among Nigerian graduates increased from 2.6% to 24.6%, reflecting a critical challenge within the education system. While graduate unemployment is a global phenomenon, stakeholders in developed countries have emphasized the need for vocational and technical skill acquisition to enhance employability. In response, Nigeria introduced vocational and technical education through the 6-3-3-4 system in 1982 and later the 9-3-4 system in 2007, aimed at equipping youths with practical skills, enterprise competencies, and technological literacy. This policy seeks to foster self-reliant graduates capable of generating employment, contributing positively to society, and addressing the unemployment crisis.</p>	<p>Graduate unemployment, Vocational education, Technical skills, Employability; Self-reliance.</p>

INTRODUCTION

There have been burning issues in Nigeria education system which have directly affected the national economy beyond expectations. Paramount of such issues that affect the economic growth and development negatively in Nigeria is high rate of unemployment among graduates of higher institutions of learning. Unemployment of graduates of higher institutions in Nigeria has eaten deep into the fabrics of the nation's economy. Adejimola and Olutunilayo (2009) observed that about 80% of graduates from Nigerian universities find it extremely difficult to secure employment on graduation on yearly basis. According to National Bureau of Statistics (2017), the unemployment rate of Nigerian graduates from higher institutions rose from 2.6% in 2006 to 24.6% in 2017. Be that as it may, graduates' unemployment is not peculiar to Nigeria or developing nations alone, it is indeed a long standing global phenomenon.

In tackling this global and ugly trend of unemployment, policy makers and stakeholders in developing countries such as England, United States of America and Germany advocated a refocus of educational systems towards

acquisition of vocational and technical skills to enhance the smooth transition into jobs for graduates of universities. It in this regard that vocational and technical education was introduced into the educational system of Nigeria through the introduction of the 6-3-4 system of education in 1982, and now 9-3-4 system of education in 2007 aimed at providing training and inculcating necessary skills geared towards the production of craftsmen, technicians and other skillful youths who will possess enterprise skills and also have understanding of the increasing dynamism of technology (FRN, 2014). One of the goals of the policy was to train youths that would help to create jobs for themselves after school and become self-reliant citizens who are responsive and responsible to Nigerian society. In recognition of the inability of the economy to absorb the teeming unemployed youths, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the National Education Research Development Council (NERDC) proposed the introduction of entrepreneurship education in the entire school curriculum particularly at higher institutions of learning in Nigeria.

The introduction of entrepreneurship education into Nigerian institutions of higher learning is a response to the international call and the need to curb the high rate of unemployment globally to reduce the reliance on government paid jobs which hitherto has manifested greatly in developing countries like Nigeria (UNESCO, 2010). The entrepreneurship education is to be taught by qualified entrepreneurs. An entrepreneur is a person that takes risks, has initiatives and creativity and makes things happen through the skills bestowed on the person (Obosode, 2009). The skills that will enable individuals operate their jobs or businesses have to be taught in schools by the lecturers so as to realize the self-reliant bid of the government. The entrepreneurship education curriculum offers subjects like basic technology education and basic business education to enable individual students acquire the entrepreneurial skills which will enhance self-employment opportunity.

The attainment of the objectives of entrepreneurship education is critical and requires lecturers that are knowledgeable and competent to implement the entrepreneurship education curriculum in tertiary institutions. This is realized through the acquisition of certain levels of skills by the lecturers saddled with the interpretation of the curriculum. Competency are skills or knowledge required of the lecturers for the teaching of the entrepreneurship education in the classroom situation. Competency in the view of Hobson (2009) involves having a sound knowledge of the subject matter and of the methods of effectively imparting the facts and skills relating to the subject. These skills are skills in management, accounting and financial skills, marketing and sale skills and general business competencies. Although these skills are quite indispensable and invariably a requisite for school managerial position, it is important to note that there is still poor teaching of entrepreneurship education in our high institutions of leaning. This is manifested on the extent that greater number of graduates from the high institutions do graduate and continue to remain unemployed. It is because of this, it has been stated that the rate of unemployment is usually on the increase as graduates solely depend on government while white collar jobs are not there and believe that if entrepreneurs education is properly carried out, people will be more independent and the issue of unemployment will be a thing of the past. Eze, Ezenwafor and Igbalarha (2016) maintained that entrepreneurship education has a spiral effect of ensuring sustainable development and growth in a country like Nigeria. Equally, entrepreneurship education enables students of tertiary institution to acquire lifelong entrepreneurship skills. It is important to note that through entrepreneurship education, students including those with disabilities learn organizational skills including time management, leadership development and entrepreneurial skills, all of which are highly transferable skills sought by employers of labour. Be that as it may, there is still poor performance of lecturers in entrepreneurship education which can be seen in students' poor achievement in terms of entrepreneurship skill acquisition. This was why Emejulu (2014) maintained that most lecturers that teach entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions lack skills and competencies in computer

network knowledge, software application, multimedia technology, World Wide Web (www) networking, and internet connectivity used in higher institutions.

Similarly, some lecturers seem not to have managerial competencies, and as such waste a lot of time in trying to harmonize issues in the classroom. This slows down the teaching of entrepreneurship in the classroom transcending to students' inability to acquire skills. There some time consuming activities which lecturers engage themselves and this make them not to succeed in their teaching, hence low acquisition of entrepreneurial skills by students. According to Dutt and Crossan (2005) some common time consuming activities include but not limited to slow decision making, inability to delegate, unnecessary interruptions, appointments that fail to take place, delays while traveling, poorly conducted meeting, and procrastination. Therefore, for successful teaching of entrepreneurship education, lecturers should possess the skills of management.

Financial management skills are another critical factor which lecturers should possess while teaching students entrepreneurship education. This is important to avoid wastage of the scarce financial resources available. Skills in financial management include ability to allocate funds available, ability to make good financial budgets for new business, competencies in inventory and good record keeping skills. It is expected that young entrepreneur should possess these competencies to be able to meet up with job demand in this global competitiveness. However, corruption has changed the financial management at various sectors of economy of Nigeria. This was why Enyi (2009) stated that corruption and mediocrity of personnel pervaded many revenue generating activities in Nigeria. It is because of this increasing poor instructional performance of lecturers as reported by National University Commission (NUC) which obviously manifest in students' poor achievement in terms of entrepreneurship skill acquisition, government has resolved to lay emphasis on competencies required of lecturers in teaching entrepreneurship education. In Ebonyi State University, management for instance, resolved to make all logistics available for adequate and proper teaching of entrepreneurship education.

Although, lecturers' effective instructional performance could be achieved through relevant competency skills, it is equally necessary to assess a detailed specific competency required of lecturers in teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent cases of poor teaching of educational programmes especially as it concerns the entrepreneurship education occasioned by instructional incompetency of teachers and poor academic on the part of students are issues of great concern not only to the education industry but also to the entire society. This ugly situation coupled with high rate of unemployment of youths in the country tends to generate doubt as to whether entrepreneurship education lecturers are carrying out their instructional delivery very effectively. Although researcher have associated these problems to inadequate competencies of teachers in teaching entrepreneurship education, they have not been able to establish the extent of competencies required by lecturers for teaching of entrepreneurship education as they relate to ICT, managerial and financial management competencies.

In Ebonyi State, competencies required of lecturers in the teaching of entrepreneurship education are still based on theoretical speculations without empirical backing. Therefore, the template on which competencies required of lecturers in the teaching of entrepreneurship education could be transcribed as still lacking and so constitute a challenge to researchers in educational administration. Therefore, this paper explored the specific competencies required of lecturers in teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State.

Purpose of the Study.

The main purpose of this study is to investigate the extent lecturers possess competencies needed for teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study focused on:

1. Determining the extent lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.
2. Ascertain the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.
3. Explore the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

Research Questions

The following three research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent do lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions?
2. To what extent do lectures possess managerial competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent do lecturers possess financial management competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary in situations?

Hypothesis.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess CT competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions?
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Among the participants in the research were 188 lecturers from Ebonyi State University's Department of Education in Abakaliki, 197 lecturers from Alex Ekwueme Federal University in Ndufu Alike Ikwo, Ebonyi State, and 126 lecturers from Ebonyi State College of Education Ikwo and 136 lecturers from Uwana Federal Polytechnics,

Afikpo. As a result, 647 instructors, both male and female, were produced. The full population Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK was used for the research, hence there was no sampling. The instrument for data collection is the researchers self-developed questionnaire titled, "Competencies possessed for Teaching of Entrepreneurship Education Questionnaire Scale" (CPTEEQS). It is a four-point scale instrument of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) rated 4, 3, 1 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in the department of Educational Foundations and one from Measurement and Evaluation in Science Education, all from Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the researchers administered forty copies of the instrument to forty lecturers of Enugu State University of Science and Technology. The responses of the lecturers were collected and subjected to measures of internal reliability index of 0.60. Data collected were analyzed using mean scores and standard deviations, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any mean score from 2.50 and above was considered Very High and High extent, while any mean score from 2.49 and below in adjudged low and very low extent.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent do lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions?

Table1: Mean Scores of responses on the extent lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1.	Competency in software management	1.84	0.61	LE
2.	Competency in search information in digital environments	1.84	0.62	LE
3.	Competency in social networking tools to successfully function in a knowledge economy	1.92	0.54	LE
4.	Competency in judging the appropriateness of information	1.86	0.62	LE
5.	Competency in presenting information properly in ICT environments	1.95	0.52	LE
Grand Mean Score		1.81	0.51	LE

Result on table 1 showed that the lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary education institution in Ebonyi State to a low extent. The grand score which is 1.81 with standard deviation of 1.51 is an indication that lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions to a low extent.

Research Question2: To what extent do lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

Table 2: Mean ratings of lecturers on the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions of Ebonyi State?

<u>S/N</u>	<u>Items</u>	<u>Mean</u>	<u>SD</u>	<u>Decision.</u>
6	Competency in development of good attitudes to the teaching of entrepreneurship education	2.25	0.54	LE
7.	competency on working practice to mobilize for teaching entrepreneurship education	2.10	0.58	LE
8.	Competency on interpersonal relation to enhance teaching of entrepreneurship education	2.15	0.58	LE
9.	Competency in advocating organizational changes necessary in keeping to talent to enhance teaching of entrepreneurship education	1.84	0.61	LE
10.	Competency in dealing with risk management in teaching of entrepreneurship education	2.02	0.63	LE
Grand Mean Score		2.07	0.54	LE

Result on table 2 indicates that lecturers do not possess managerial competencies in teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary. The grand mean of 2.07 with standard deviation of 0.54 which is below the criterion mean of 2.50 authenticated the above statement.

Research Question 3: To what extent do lecturers possess financial management competencies in the teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions?

Table3: Mean score of lecturers on the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies in teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
11.	Competency in financial budgeting allocation	2.25	0.54	LE
12.	Competency in sourcing of funds for business growth	2.25	0.54	LE
13.	Competency in identifying financial investment opportunities	1.85	0.61	LE
14.	Competency in managing internet financial crimes to ensure sustainability of business	1.81	0.56	LE
15	Competency in programme sustainable management accounting in modern sophisticated business environment	1.88	0.62	LE
16.	Competency in modern method of financial record keeping	1.85	0.61	LE
Grand Mean Score		1.98	0.54	LE

Result on table 3 showed that the respondents were of the opinion that lecturers possess competencies financial management for the teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions to a low extent. This was proved by the mean score of 1.98 and 0.54 standard deviation of the respondents.

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess ICT competencies in teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

Table 4: t-test of independent sample on the significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess ICT competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebony State tertiary institutions.

S/N	Variable: Gender	Mean	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit	Dec.
1.	Male	1.90	0.54	645	0.12	1.96	Not sig.
	Female	1.90	0.55				
2.	Male	2.31	0.49	645	0.20	1.96	Not sig
	Female	2.20					
3.	Male	2.31	0.58	645	1.13	1.96	Not sign
	Female	2.20					
4.	Male	1.86	0.60	645	0.98	1.96	Not sig
	Female	1.84					
5.	Male	1.87	0.63	645	1,46	1.96	Not sig
	Female	1.83					
Grand Average					0.78	1.96	Not sig.

Result of t-test analysis on table 4 showed that the t-calculated value is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 and degree of freedom (DF) of 645. The average t-calculated value of 0.98 is also less than the average t-critical value of 1.96 hence not significant. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess ICT competencies in teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

Table 5: t-test of independent sample on the significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

S/N	Variable: Gender	Mean	SD	DF	t-cal	t-crit.	Dec.
6.	Male Female	3.14 3.37	0.61 0.51	645	0.23	1.96	Not sig
7.	Male Female	3.28 3.06	0.76 0.48	645	1.44	1.96	Not sig
8.	Male Female	3.16 3.36	0.61	645	1.40	1.96	Not sig
9.	Male Female	3.29 3.08	0.47 0.54	645	0.96	1.96	not sig
10.	Male Female	3.56 3.32	0.52 0.61	645	1.13	1.96	Not sig
Grand Average					1.03	1.96	Not sig

Result on table 5 revealed that the t-calculated value is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 and degree of freedom (DF) of 645. The average t-calculated value of 1.03 is also less than the average mean of t-critical value of 1.96. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected, meaning that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess managerial competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions of Ebonyi State.

3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions of Ebonyi State.

Table 6: t-test of independent sample on the significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies for teaching of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

S/N	Variable: Gender	Mean	SD	DF	t-cal	t-critical	Dec.
11.	Male Female	3.42 3.26	0.51 0.72	645	1.69	1.69	Not sig
12.	Male Female	3.24 3.34	0.64	645	0.81	1.96	Not sig
13.	Male Female	3.11 3.18	0.60 0.72		0.53	1.96	Not sig

				645				
14.	Male	Female	2.75	0.76	645	0.36	1.96	Not sig
			2.69	0.87				
15.	Male	Female	3.76	0.43				Not sig
			3.53	0.54	645	1.65	1.96	
	Grand Average					1.01	1.96	Not sig

Table 6 displays the results of the t-test analysis, which showed that the computed t-value is less than the t-critical value of 1.96. The average t-calculated value of 1.01 is also less than the average t-critical value of 1.96. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female lecturers on the extent lecturers possess financial management competencies in the teaching of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions in Ebonyi State. In this regard the null hypothesis was accepted.

DISCUSSIONS

Results on table one shows that lecturers do not possess ICT competencies for teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions of Ebonyi State. This ugly situation is a serious threat to full realization of entrepreneurship education programmes objectives. When the lecturers do not possess ICT competencies, it will lead to poor acquisition of skills by the students and in this way the programme will be a mere paper work. It is in this regard that Emejulu (2014) remarked that most lecturers that teach entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions lack skills and competencies in computer network knowledge, software application, multimedia technology, World Wide Web (www) networking and internet connectivity used in high institutions.

Result on table two showed that lecturers also do not possess the managerial competencies in teaching of entrepreneurship education. If the lecturers teaching entrepreneurship education do not have the skills in management of the class size, time, space and the scarce equipment, such lecturer will-perform poorly in his teaching activities. In some cases, there are some time-consuming activities which some lecturers engage themselves in instead of the proper teaching. These include slow decision making, inability to delegate and so on. This is in agreement with Dutt and Crossan (2005) who stated that some lecturers spend a lot of time in decision making, inability to delegate, Publication of the European Centre for Research Training and Development-UK unnecessary interruptions, appointment that fail to take place, delays while travelling, poorly conducted meetings and procrastinations. The inability of the lecturers to manage the environment well will hinder the objectives of entrepreneurship education in Ebonyi State tertiary institutions.

Result on table three indicates that lecturers do not equally possess competencies in financial management as it concerns teaching of entrepreneurship education. Funds are scarce, and the little one available should be prudently managed to avoid wastage. Skills in financial management include ability to allocate funds available, ability to make good financial budgets for new businesses, competencies in inventory and good record keeping. However, corruption has changed the financial management at various sectors of Nigerian economy. This is in line with Enyi (2001) who stated that corruption and mediocrity of personnel's pervaded many revenue generation activities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The importance of lectures possessing the competencies in teaching entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions of Ebonyi State University cannot be disputed. The Federal Government of Nigeria introduced entrepreneurship education in the tertiary institutions to reduce unemployment rate of university graduates, reduce poverty and help graduates become self-employed and selfreliant on graduation. The attainment of this lofty objectives depends on lecturers being knowledgeable and competent to implement the entrepreneurship education

curriculum in tertiary institutions. Therefore, all stakeholders and managers in the education industry should put every logistics in place to realize the good dreams of the Federal government in making our university graduates employable on graduation.

Recommendations:

Based on the study's results, the following suggestions were made:

1. Government should continue to re-train lecturers in the use of ICT in teaching entrepreneurship education.
2. Government should make organization of workshops and seminars on management and teaching of entrepreneurship education an annual event so that lecturers will become abreast with the new trend in management.
3. Government should provide avenue for blocking all the loopholes for financial frauds in the tertiary institutions, especially money meant for the implementation of the entrepreneurship education programmes.

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